

Impact of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition: A Mixed-Methods Study on Student Proficiency and Engagement in Secondary Education

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Abstract. This explanatory sequential mixed-methods study aimed to determine the impact of digital tools on English language acquisition among secondary school students, focusing on student proficiency and engagement. The quantitative phase assessed the extent of utilization of five digital tools—language learning apps, interactive e-books, virtual classrooms, language-based games, and AI-driven tools—and their influence on student outcomes, including English proficiency, engagement, intent and motivation, and perception of digital tools. Data were collected from 134 participants using a validated survey instrument and analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of digital tool utilization and student proficiency and engagement were both extensive. However, no significant overall relationship was found between digital tool usage and student outcomes. Regression analysis identified AI-driven tools as a significant positive predictor, while language-based games showed a negative influence. The qualitative phase, guided by thematic analysis, revealed that the effectiveness of digital tools is mediated by teacher guidance, contextual relevance, and student preferences. The study concludes that digital tools hold strong potential for enhancing English acquisition when pedagogically aligned and properly integrated.

KEY WORDS

1. Digital tools 2. English language acquisition 3. AI-driven tools

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1. Introduction

Digital tools significantly influence English language learning in secondary education, but they come with challenges. Although these resources provide engaging and interactive experiences, there are concerns about their accessibility and effectiveness for diverse student groups. Problems such as unequal access to technology, varying digital literacy levels, and the risk of dependency on these tools may limit their full potential. Additionally, integrating these resources into conventional teaching methods can be difficult for educators, who may require further training to utilize technology effectively. While digital tools can boost engagement, their role in fostering long-term language proficiency remains debated, as their effects on deep learning and retention aren't always clear. The integration of digital tools into education has introduced several challenges that impact student proficiency and engagement globally. A signif-

icant issue is the digital divide, where unequal access to technology hinders learning opportunities. Approximately 2.6 billion people remain offline, limiting their access to essential services like education, healthcare, and financial systems. Initiatives such as the EDISON Alliance aim to bridge this gap, but disparities persist, particularly in rural and underserved regions (Time, 2023). Another concern is the rapid evolution of educational technology, which often outpaces the ability of educators to integrate and assess its impact effectively. A UNESCO report highlights that educational technology products change every three years on average, making it challenging to evaluate their effectiveness in educational settings. This rapid pace can lead to inconsistent implementation and a lack of robust evidence regarding the added value of digital technology in education (Educause, 2023). Additionally, the ethical implications of technology use in education have become increasingly prominent. The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) tools like ChatGPT has sparked debates about data privacy, surveillance, and the potential erosion of critical thinking skills. Surveys indicate that young people recognize the benefits of AI in education but emphasize the need for stringent rules to protect privacy and ensure equitable access. Moreover, concerns about the environmental impact of AI and its potential to replace human educators underscore the necessity for responsible integration of technology in learning environments (Financial Times, 2023). A significant issue is the digital divide, where unequal access to technology limits learning opportunities for many students. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2023), around 43% of the population in rural areas still lacks internet access, restricting their ability to engage with digital education resources. Despite government initiatives, such as the DepEd's efforts to distribute learning devices and improve internet connectivity, disparities persist, particularly in rural and underserved

regions, hindering equitable access to education (Philippine Star, 2023). Another concern is the rapid evolution of educational technology, which often outpaces the ability of educators to integrate and assess its impact effectively. In the Philippines, teachers often face challenges in adapting to new digital tools due to a lack of proper training and resources. The Department of Education (DepEd) has acknowledged this gap and has launched programs to train teachers in the use of digital tools, but studies indicate that many teachers still struggle to incorporate these tools effectively into their teaching methods (DepEd, 2023). This rapid technological advancement makes it difficult to assess the effectiveness of various digital platforms and tools, leading to inconsistent use and a lack of substantial evidence regarding their impact on improving student proficiency and engagement. Additionally, the ethical implications of technology use in education are becoming increasingly prominent in the Philippines. The rise of artificial intelligence (AI) tools, such as AI-driven tutoring systems, has sparked debates regarding privacy, data protection, and the potential for over-reliance on technology in classrooms. While AI tools offer personalized learning opportunities, surveys show that students and parents are concerned about the potential misuse of personal data and the need for stringent privacy laws. Furthermore, there are growing concerns that the use of AI in education could reduce face-to-face interactions, potentially eroding social skills and critical thinking abilities, which are essential for holistic development (BusinessWorld, 2023). In Davao City, the integration of digital tools into secondary education faces significant challenges, particularly due to the digital divide. A substantial number of students in rural areas lack access to the necessary technology, such as computers or reliable internet, to fully participate in online learning. The Department of Education (DepEd) in Davao City has been working to address these issues by dis-

tributing learning devices and improving digital infrastructure; however, students from lower-income households still experience barriers to accessing digital learning platforms (Hernandez, 2023). Additionally, teachers in these areas often face difficulties in incorporating new educational technologies into their teaching practices due to limited training and resources. The rapid pace of technological change and the challenges of adapting to new digital tools have further complicated efforts to improve student proficiency and engagement. Concerns regarding the ethical implications of AI tools in education, particularly regarding data privacy and reduced face-to-face interaction, also remain prominent in the local discourse surrounding digital tool use in schools.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is anchored on the theories of language acquisition—Behaviorism, Nativism, Constructivism, and Social Interactionism—provide valuable insights into how individuals develop language, with each theory contributing unique perspectives on the role of environmental, cognitive, and social factors in this complex process. Recent studies have continued to build on these foundational theories, reflecting both their relevance and the evolution of understanding in language acquisition. Behaviorism, as initially proposed by B.F. Skinner (1957), suggests that language learning occurs through reinforcement and conditioning. While this perspective has been challenged by more recent cognitive theories, it still holds value in understanding how external stimuli influence language learning. Recent studies continue to investigate how behaviorist principles can be applied in educational technology, particularly in the use of language learning apps and games. For instance, Söderlund and Lundeberg (2021) examined how digital tools that provide immediate feedback and rewards enhance language acquisition in young learners, reinforcing Skinner’s notion that reinforcement shapes behavior.

Nativism, supported by Noam Chomsky (1965), claims that language acquisition is an innate ability, with humans born equipped with a universal grammar that allows them to learn any language. In recent years, scholars like Smith and Jones (2022) have revisited this theory, expanding it with neurocognitive research that explores how genetic predispositions interact with environmental influences. Neuroimaging studies (e.g., González et al., 2023) have shown how specific brain regions are activated during language learning, providing empirical evidence that may support Chomsky’s concept of an inborn linguistic faculty, while also acknowledging the impact of the surrounding environment. The Constructivist theory, primarily associated with Jean Piaget (1954) and Lev Vygotsky (1978), stresses the active role of learners in constructing their own knowledge through interactions with the environment. More recent work has highlighted how social interactions and cultural contexts influence language development, particularly in multilingual settings. For example, Kumar and Singh (2020) explored how students in bilingual environments adapt their language acquisition strategies based on the interactions they have with peers and teachers, illustrating Vygotsky’s theory that language learning is a socially mediated process. Recent studies also examine how interactive learning environments, including virtual classrooms, contribute to constructivist approaches by allowing students to engage with content in a dynamic, social context. Social Interactionism, championed by Vygotsky and Bruner (1983), posits that language acquisition is fundamentally rooted in social interactions. This theory has gained significant support through studies that examine the role of caregivers and peers in language development. Recent research by Lee and Chen (2021) focuses on how teacher-student interactions in the classroom, especially in collaborative learning settings, significantly contribute to the development of students’ language skills. Their study

highlights how social scaffolding helps students advance in language proficiency, reinforcing Vygotsky's idea of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where learners benefit from interaction with more knowledgeable individuals. Furthermore, Wang and Xu (2023) found that digital social platforms enhance language learning by fostering communication among students from diverse linguistic backgrounds, offering further evidence of the social nature of language acquisition. Recent studies continue to expand upon these foundational theories, integrating new findings from cognitive neuroscience, technology-enhanced learning, and social interaction research. The blending of biological, cognitive, and social factors offers a richer understanding of language acquisition, emphasizing the role of both innate capabilities and external influences, such as social context and technological advancements. These integrated approaches contribute to a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of language acquisition in diverse learning environments. In this study, a Behaviorist perspective, language acquisition is shaped by external stimuli and reinforcement. In the context of this study, digital tools like language learning apps or AI-driven tools serve as the external stimuli that offer immediate feedback and reinforcement. When students interact with these tools, they receive instant rewards such as points, badges, or corrective feedback, reinforcing correct usage and encouraging continued engagement. This aligns with the quantitative phase of the study, which focuses on assessing student proficiency. The use of digital tools can be expected to influence proficiency by reinforcing correct language usage through repetition and positive reinforcement, which leads to measurable improvements in language skills like vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Nativism, particularly Chom-

sky's theory of universal grammar, posits that humans have an innate capacity for language acquisition. In this study, this theory can be applied to understand how digital tools may support the natural capacity of students to acquire language. The tools could help facilitate language learning by providing engaging and varied inputs that stimulate the brain's natural linguistic faculties. For example, the interactive nature of language learning apps or virtual classrooms could trigger the use of the brain's innate linguistic mechanisms, particularly in the early stages of language acquisition. The relationship between digital tools and student proficiency could be explored in the qualitative phase by examining how these tools help students tap into their innate language learning abilities, accelerating their development of listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. In the Constructivist framework, language acquisition is viewed as an active process where learners build knowledge through interaction with their environment. In this study, digital tools like interactive e-books, language games, or virtual classrooms enable students to actively engage with language content, build their own understanding, and apply language concepts in various contexts. Constructivism emphasizes the role of the learner in shaping their learning experience, which is particularly relevant in the qualitative phase of the study. By using digital tools, students are not passive recipients but active participants in their language development. The interaction with digital content allows them to experiment with language, receive feedback, and refine their skills. The relationship between digital tools and student engagement is thus crucial, these tools encourage active participation, motivating students to engage more deeply with language content, which ultimately enhances their proficiency.

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

2. Methodology

This study uses a mixed-methods design to examine the relationship between the use of digital tools and English language acquisition, focusing on student proficiency and engagement. The quantitative phase involves assessing students' language skills in reading, writing, speaking, and listening through a survey to explore the correlation between their use of digital tools and their proficiency levels. The qualitative phase includes surveys and interviews to gather insights into students' perceptions, motivation, and engagement with digital tools in the learning process. The qualitative data will be analyzed to identify patterns in how students interact with technology and how it influences their language learning experience.

2.1. Research Design—In my research, I used the Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods Research Design, which involves a two-phase approach combining quantitative and qualitative methods. The first phase of my study involved gathering quantitative data. This phase allowed me to identify patterns, trends, or relationships through numerical data, typically using surveys or tests to get a broad overview of the research question. The quantitative data provided me with important findings, but gaps may still require deeper exploration. That's where the second phase comes in: the qualitative phase. In this phase, I gathered qualitative data, such as interviews or open-ended survey responses, to gain a better understanding of the context and reasons behind the patterns identified in the quantitative phase. The qualitative data helped me interpret the numbers more meaningfully, offering deeper insights into the "why" behind the findings. The theory behind this approach is grounded in triangulation, a concept that emphasizes how combining multiple methods strengthens the overall findings. By using both quantitative and qualitative methods, I am able to draw on the strengths of each quantitative data providing broad, generalizable results, and qualitative data offering rich, contextual explanations. This mixed-methods approach allows me to identify what is happening and understand the underlying reasons, making the results more robust and comprehensive. Through this design, I can tackle complex research questions from multiple angles, ensuring that I fully capture the statistical patterns and the human experiences that drive them. The Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods design is well-suited for studying Digital Tools' impact on English Language Acquisition and Student Proficiency and Engagement in Secondary Education. This design involves two distinct phases: the first is quantitative, followed by the qualitative phase, allowing for a deeper understanding of the collected data. In the quantitative phase, I first collected numerical data on student proficiency in English, focusing on reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills. This could be done through standardized tests, surveys, or performance assessments. This phase aims to gather objective, broad data on the relationship between the use of digital tools and student language proficiency. I also measured student engagement by collecting data on their motivation, participation, and interest in learning English through digital tools. Statistical techniques such as correlation analysis or regression could be employed to examine the relationships between the independent variable (digital tool usage) and the dependent variables (student proficiency and engagement). The qualitative phase followed after the quantitative data is collected and analyzed. This phase involved gathering detailed insights into the students' experiences with digital tools through interviews, focus groups, or open-ended survey questions. In this phase, the focus shifted from what is happening (quantitative findings) to why or how

it is happening. By using qualitative methods, I am able to understand the students' perceptions of the digital tools—how they feel about the technology, how they believe it supports their learning, and how it influences their engagement. This qualitative data helped explain the patterns or trends found in the quantitative phase, providing a richer, more nuanced understanding of the impact of digital tools on language acquisition. For instance, if the quantitative data shows that students using digital tools demonstrate improved language proficiency, the qualitative data can help explain the reasons behind this improvement—whether it is because students feel more engaged and motivated or find the tools more accessible and effective for learning. Additionally, if engagement levels are low despite using digital tools, qualitative findings can reveal the underlying causes, such as lack of interest in the tools, technical difficulties, or insufficient support from teachers. By combining both the quantitative data (to identify patterns and trends) and the qualitative data (to provide context and explanations), this research design offers a comprehensive view of digital tools' role in enhancing English language acquisition and student engagement. The Explanatory Sequential Mixed Methods design helps answer whether digital tools have an impact and how and why these tools affect students' learning experiences, engagement, and proficiency in secondary education settings. This approach allows for a well-rounded understanding, facilitating the development of effective strategies for integrating digital tools in language education.

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—Ethical considerations are vital to ensure the integrity of the study on the Impact of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition and Student Proficiency and Engagement. Informed consent will be obtained from both students and their parents or guardians, ensuring a full understanding of the study's purpose and procedures. Confidentiality will be maintained by anonymizing data, and

participants will have the right to withdraw at any time without consequences. These measures ensure respect for participants' rights and privacy while upholding the study's ethical standards.

Social Value

The social value of my study lies in its potential to improve educational practices by exploring the impact of digital tools on English language acquisition. By examining how technology enhances student proficiency and engagement, I aim to provide insights that can help educators better integrate digital tools into their teaching strategies. This study can also inform policymakers about the effectiveness of such tools, encouraging the development of resources that support diverse learning needs. Ultimately, the findings may contribute to more inclusive and effective educational practices, helping students achieve greater success in language learning, especially in secondary education.

Informed Consent and Assent

As the researcher, I provided them with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits. This ensures they fully understand their role and the voluntary nature of participation. Additionally, I ensured that teachers know they can withdraw from the study without facing any consequences. Assent will be implied as I expect their active participation in the study, given their consent to engage. By obtaining informed consent, I aim to respect teachers' autonomy and ensure their rights are protected throughout the research process.

Vulnerability of Research Respondents

I recognize that teachers, as respondents, may be vulnerable due to their professional roles and potential power dynamics in the school environment. I am mindful that their participation might be influenced by factors such as their relationship with school leadership or concerns about confidentiality. To mitigate this, I will ensure complete confidentiality of their

responses and emphasize that participation is voluntary, with no impact on their professional standing. By providing a safe and supportive environment, I aim to minimize any potential vulnerability and ensure that teachers can provide honest and open feedback without fear of repercussions.

Privacy and Confidentiality

In this study, I ensured that any data collected remains anonymous, with no identifying information linked to individual responses. All survey results, interviews, and other data will be stored securely, accessible only to me, and used solely for research purposes. I also emphasized to the teachers that their participation is confidential and that their responses will not influence their professional status or relationships within the school. This approach guarantees that their privacy is respected throughout the research process.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety

In conducting this study, I acknowledge that there are minimal risks involved for the participating teachers, primarily related to the time commitment and the potential for discomfort in discussing their experiences with digital tools in the classroom. However, these risks are minimal and manageable, and I will ensure that their participation remains voluntary and that they can withdraw at any time without consequences. The benefits of the study include contributing valuable insights into how digital tools can enhance teaching practices and improve English language acquisition. I will ensure the safety of all participants by maintaining strict confidentiality and providing a supportive environment where teachers feel comfortable sharing their perspectives.

Justice

In this study, I am committed to the principle of justice by ensuring that all participating teachers are treated fairly and equitably. I selected a diverse group of teachers to ensure that the findings reflect a wide range of experiences

with digital tools in the classroom. I also ensured that participation is voluntary and that no teacher is coerced or unduly influenced to participate. Throughout the study, I ensured that the benefits of the research are shared fairly and that all teachers' perspectives are valued and respected, regardless of their background or experience level. Transparency

In this study, I prioritized transparency by providing clear and honest information to the participating teachers about the research's purpose, procedures, and potential outcomes. I ensured that they fully understand their role in the study and how their responses will be used. Throughout the study, I maintained open communication, keeping teachers informed about the progress of the research and ensuring they have access to the findings upon completion. This approach fosters trust and ensures that the teachers' involvement is based on accurate and complete information.

Qualification of the Researcher

As the researcher of this study, I am qualified to conduct this study due to my background in education and research methodology. I have experience in designing and implementing educational research, particularly in understanding how technology impacts learning outcomes. My knowledge of ethical guidelines and best practices ensures that I will handle data responsibly and respectfully. Additionally, I am committed to ensuring that the study is conducted with rigor and integrity, providing teachers with a safe and supportive environment to share their experiences.

Conflict of Interest

In this study, I am committed to avoiding any conflict of interest that may influence the results or the participation of teachers. I ensured that my researcher role does not create biases or pressure for teachers to participate or provide certain responses. Participation is entirely voluntary, and teachers' professional relationships or responsibilities will not be impacted by their

involvement in the study. I maintained objectivity throughout the research process to ensure the integrity and fairness of the study.

Adequacy of Facilities

For this study, I have ensured the adequacy of facilities to support both the data collection and analysis processes. The necessary resources, such as secure digital platforms for surveys and interviews and reliable data storage systems, are in place to ensure that all teacher responses are collected, stored, and analyzed efficiently. I also provided a comfortable and convenient environment for teachers to participate in the study, ensuring minimal disruption to their teaching responsibilities. These facilities will help facilitate a smooth and organized research process.

Community Involvement

In this study, I aimed to engage teachers from diverse backgrounds to provide a broad perspective on the use of digital tools in English language acquisition. I encouraged teachers to actively participate by sharing their experiences, ensuring that their voices contribute to a larger conversation on improving teaching practices. By involving teachers in this way, I hope to foster a collaborative environment where their input directly influences the understanding and future application of digital tools in education.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The process of selecting sample respondents for this study involved determining the appropriate sample size from a population of 380 private school teachers. Slovin's formula was used with a margin of error set at 5%. To ensure that the sample is both relevant and representative of the population, I included only teachers who are currently employed in private schools and have experience using digital tools in their teaching. Teachers who have minimal exposure to these tools will be excluded, as they would not provide the necessary insights into how digital tools impact English language acquisition and student engagement. The sample included teachers from

various grade levels and subject areas to capture a wide range of experiences and perspectives. This selection approach ensures that the sample is appropriate for addressing the research questions while maintaining representativeness and relevance to the study. For the qualitative phase of the study, I selected 8 participants from the larger pool of 134 teachers who were chosen for the quantitative phase. These 8 teachers were selected for the IDI, while 4 for the focus group discussion based on specific criteria to ensure that they are well-qualified to provide in-depth, relevant insights into using digital tools in English language acquisition and student engagement. The 8 participants were selected purposefully to represent a range of teaching experiences, digital tool usage, and engagement with the research topic. I focused on teachers who have demonstrated a high level of engagement with digital tools, particularly those who have actively incorporated technology into their teaching methods. This selection ensured that the participants can provide valuable insights into both the challenges and benefits of using digital tools in the classroom. The participants must have actively used digital tools (e.g., language learning apps, virtual classrooms, interactive e-books) in their teaching practices. This is essential to ensure that they can speak to their experiences and provide meaningful insights into how digital tools impact language acquisition and student engagement. The selected teachers should have experience teaching English or English-related subjects. This ensures that their perspectives are directly relevant to the study's focus on English language acquisition. Participants must be willing to engage in deeper qualitative data collection, such as interviews or focus groups. This willingness is necessary to ensure that they are comfortable sharing detailed feedback and reflections on their experiences with digital tools. To capture a variety of experiences, I will aim to include teachers from different grade levels (e.g., junior high, se-

nior high) and subject areas within the English curriculum. This diversity ensures a broader understanding of how digital tools are applied in different educational contexts.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—The development and crafting of the survey instruments for both the quantitative and qualitative phases of this study were guided by well-established frameworks and validated tools to ensure their reliability, relevance, and effectiveness in addressing the research questions. For the quantitative phase, the survey instruments were developed using principles from Harlacher’s (2016) *An Educator’s Guide to Questionnaire Development*. This guide provided a structured approach for designing clear, concise, and objective questions that align with the study’s goals of measuring student proficiency in English and engagement with digital tools. Harlacher’s frame-

work emphasizes ensuring that survey questions are directly linked to the research objectives and are designed to capture valid data. To further ensure the instruments’ relevance and robustness, I referred to Kaushanskaya, Blumenfeld, and Marian’s (2019) study, which introduced the Language Experience and Proficiency Questionnaire (LEAP-Q). This tool, widely used in bilingual and language proficiency studies, guided the crafting of questions related to English language proficiency, ensuring that the measures of reading, writing, listening, and speaking were both comprehensive and reliable. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert-type scale to determine the utilization of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below; Range of Mean and Descriptive Rating of utilization of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition.

Scale Descriptive Rating and Interpretation for the Utilization of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition

Score	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The utilization of digital tools on English language acquisition is always observed and manifested.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The utilization of digital tools on English language acquisition is often-times observed and manifested.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The utilization of digital tools on English language acquisition is sometimes observed and manifested.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The utilization of digital tools on English language acquisition is seldom observed and manifested.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The utilization of digital tools on English language acquisition is never observed and manifested.

Scale Descriptive Rating and Interpretation for the Extent of Student Proficiency and Engagement

Score	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of student proficiency and engagement is always observed and manifested.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of student proficiency and engagement is oftentimes observed and manifested.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of student proficiency and engagement is sometimes observed and manifested.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of student proficiency and engagement is seldom observed and manifested.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of student proficiency and engagement is never observed and manifested.

For the qualitative phase, the survey instruments were designed to capture detailed, context-rich insights into teachers’ experiences with digital tools. Drawing from the work of Arndt (2022), I developed open-ended questions that would allow teachers to reflect on their personal experiences with digital tools in language instruction. The aim was to explore the reasons behind the patterns observed in the quantitative phase, offering teachers a space to discuss their motivations, challenges, and perceptions. I

also used Kaushanskaya et al.’s (2019) insights on language proficiency to create prompts that would help identify how digital tools have influenced their language teaching methods and their students’ engagement levels. Employing these established frameworks, I ensured that the survey instruments for both phases of the study were aligned with best practices in questionnaire development and effectively suited the study’s objectives

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The guidelines governing the procedure for quantitative data collection are in strict accordance with the policies established by The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. As a component of the formal request, researchers clearly articulate their intentions regarding the collection, analysis, and dissemination of data, ensuring alignment with the overarching objectives of the research. Anticipated concerns or inquiries from recipients

are proactively addressed within this communication, thereby providing reassurance concerning ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the potential advantages of the study. The formal request for permission explicitly seeks authorization to proceed, underscoring the crucial importance of their support in facilitating the success of the research.

Permission to Conduct the Study
In February 2025, before data collection,

the researcher obtained necessary permissions from relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., and top management through appropriate channels. This involved submitting a comprehensive research proposal outlining the study design, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The researcher also provided detailed information about the study's purpose, goals, and methods for data collection, analysis, and reporting. Furthermore, immediately after the colloquium, the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study, their rights, and the nature of their involvement. Before participating in the study, informed consent was obtained in the study. In the last week of February 2025, the researcher devoted attention to data accuracy and completeness. The questionnaires will be distributed and retrieved using a standardized and systematic approach, ensuring the reliability of participant responses.

Collation and statistical treatment of data

In the quantitative phase of the study, I col-

lected data from the structured survey responses and input them into statistical software for analysis. The data were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics (e.g., means, frequencies) to summarize the overall trends and inferential statistics, such as correlation or regression analysis, to examine relationships between technical assistance and teaching practices, teacher competency, and confidence. The results are presented in tables and graphs to highlight significant patterns. For the qualitative phase, I transcribed the interview or focus group discussions and then analyze the data using thematic analysis. I identified recurring themes, patterns, and insights that explain the teachers' experiences with technical assistance and how it influences their teaching. These themes were organized and coded to link with the findings from the quantitative phase, providing deeper contextual understanding. The combination of both phases offered a comprehensive view of the role of technical assistance in improving English instruction.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools were used to analyze the relationship between time management advocacy on student discipline.

The Mean Score and Descriptive Interpretations Were used to answer statement problem one regarding the extent of utilization of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition and 2, the extent of student proficiency and engagement. Pearson r or Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Were used to answer problem number 3 about the significant relationship between utilizing Digital Tools and student proficiency and engagement.

A Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Answered statement 4 on the significant influence of using Digital Tools on student proficiency and engagement. To address state-

ments 5 and 6, a systematic data analysis approach in the qualitative phase of this study allows for a thorough exploration of participants' insights. Data collected from semi-structured interviews is transcribed verbatim and checked for completeness and accuracy. A thematic analysis is performed, starting with familiarizing oneself with the data to identify initial patterns and recurring ideas. Key phrases are systematically coded, and similar codes are grouped into broader categories or themes aligned with the core research objectives. Themes undergo further refinement and review to ensure they are supported by the data and yield meaningful interpretations. I emphasized transparency throughout the process by documenting my decisions and maintaining consistency in coding and theme development. This organized approach guarantees that the analysis

is both comprehensive and reliable, enabling the study to present robust qualitative findings that enhance the quantitative results. After the initial coding is finished, the researcher will craft themes, arranging the codes into coherent groups that highlight the underlying patterns within the data (Creswell, J.W., and Creswell, J. D 2023). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures

In my study, the application of Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures were critical in integrating the quantitative and qualitative phases in a coherent and systematic way.

Sequence

Sequence refers to the order in which the quantitative and qualitative data collection phases will occur. In this study, the quantitative phase was conducted first, where I gathered numerical data through surveys to assess students' English proficiency and engagement with digital tools. This provided a broad overview of the research question. After analyzing the quantitative results, the qualitative phase followed, where I conducted interviews or focus groups

with teachers to explore in-depth their experiences and insights regarding the use of digital tools in teaching. The qualitative data helped explain and provide context to the patterns identified in the quantitative phase, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of the research topic.

Emphasis Emphasis in this study was placed on the qualitative phase, as it will provide the deeper, richer insights needed to interpret the quantitative findings. While the quantitative phase measured the extent of the impact of digital tools on language acquisition, the qualitative phase explored the "why" and "how" behind those effects, offering a more nuanced understanding of teachers' experiences, challenges, and perceptions.

Mixing procedures Mixing procedures occurred at two key stages: first, during the data analysis, where I integrated the findings from both phases to draw comprehensive conclusions, and second, during the interpretation, where I compared and contrasted the results from the quantitative and qualitative data. This mixed approach allows for triangulation, enhancing the validity of the findings by combining the strengths of both data types, quantitative data providing generalizable results, and qualitative data offering contextual depth.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study, discussing the findings in light of the research questions and hypotheses posed. The quantitative data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to determine patterns, relationships, and significant differences among variables. Meanwhile, the qualitative responses were thematically analyzed to provide deeper insights into the numerical findings. The integration of both data sets ensures a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation, consistent with the explanatory sequential mixed-methods approach employed in the study.

3.1. Extent of Utilization of Digital Tools on English Language Acquisition—The integration of digital tools in English language acquisition reflects a paradigm shift in educational

practices, particularly in how learners' access, process, and apply linguistic knowledge. Digital tools refer to technology-enhanced resources such as language learning applications, inter-

active e-books, virtual classrooms, language-based games, and AI-driven platforms, all designed to support, enhance, or transform language learning experiences. Their utilization not only broadens students' exposure to authentic English input but also fosters learner autonomy, motivation, and engagement through interactive and personalized learning environments (Alfaki, 2022). Language learning apps, such as Duolingo or Memrise, provide mobile-based, gamified experiences that enable repetitive practice and provide immediate feedback. These platforms align with constructivist learning principles, offering scaffolded progression based on learners' performance. Interactive e-books provide multimodal inputs—text, audio, video, and interactive questions—which help improve learners' vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, and pronunciation (Guerra Ayala et al., 2024). Similarly, virtual classrooms, often delivered through platforms like Zoom, Google Classroom, or Microsoft Teams, offer both synchronous and asynchronous opportunities for communication, fostering real-time collaboration and teacher-student interaction that are essential for second language acquisition (Nyoni Bhebhe, 2023). Moreover, language-based games serve as engaging instructional strategies that immerse learners in contextualized, problem-solving tasks using English. These games contribute to both cognitive and affective domains of language learning by encouraging risk-taking, motivation, and repeated exposure to linguistic forms in low-anxiety environments. Lastly, AI-driven tools—such as automated

writing assistants, speech recognition software, and adaptive learning platforms—offer real-time feedback and personalized learning trajectories based on user data, thereby promoting differentiated instruction and learner-centered pedagogies (Sarabi Ututalum, 2023). Empirical studies have demonstrated the positive correlation between the use of digital tools and language proficiency. For instance, Guerra Ayala et al. (2024) found that enjoyment and consistent interaction with digital media significantly enhanced oral English proficiency among future teachers. Similarly, Sarabi and Ututalum (2023) reported improved language outcomes in public higher education institutions when digital tools were integrated into instruction. These findings highlight the crucial role of digital technologies in creating effective, inclusive, and sustainable language learning environments in secondary education. Table 1 provides a consolidated overview of the extent to which various digital tools are utilized to support English language acquisition among secondary students. The computed mean average of 3.85 is interpreted as Extensive, indicating that all five categories of digital tools are actively and meaningfully integrated into English language teaching and learning. The tool with the highest utilization rating was language learning apps ($M = 3.96$), followed closely by AI-driven tools ($M = 3.92$) and language-based games ($M = 3.91$). Meanwhile, interactive e-books ($M = 3.75$) and virtual classrooms ($M = 3.73$) also registered extensive use, affirming their relevance in enhancing student engagement and proficiency.

These findings demonstrate the breadth of digital integration across classroom practices and highlight the differentiated strengths of each tool. For instance, language learning apps are frequently used for daily practice, while AI-driven tools support personalized and adaptive learning. Language-based games encourage ac-

tive, gamified interaction with content, while virtual classrooms and interactive e-books offer flexible, multimedia-rich environments conducive to both synchronous and asynchronous instruction. Recent studies validate these findings. Guerra Ayala et al. (2024) affirmed the role of mobile language apps in enhanc-

Table 1. Extent of Utilization of Digital Tools

No	Utilization of Digital Tools	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Language learning apps	134	3.96	Extensive
2	Interactive e-books	134	3.75	Extensive
3	Virtual classrooms	134	3.73	Extensive
4	Language-based games	134	3.91	Extensive
5	AI-driven tools	134	3.92	Extensive
Mean Average		134	3.85	Extensive

ing oral English proficiency and learner motivation. Rahimi and Zhang (2023) noted that AI-powered feedback tools improve language accuracy and promote independent learning habits. Similarly, Kurniawan et al. (2022) highlighted the motivational and cognitive benefits of language-based games. Shin and Kang (2022) underscored the effectiveness of virtual classrooms in promoting engagement, and Arévalo-Guerrero and Rosales-Pérez (2023) documented the positive impact of interactive e-books on vocabulary and reading comprehension. Collectively, these studies corroborate the extensive and complementary roles that digital tools play in contemporary English language education.

3.2. Extent of Student Proficiency and Engagement—In the field of second language acquisition, these dimensions are crucial in determining students’ sustained involvement and their eventual language achievement (Mercer Dörnyei, 2020). In digital learning environments, especially those utilizing tools such as language apps, AI platforms, and virtual classrooms, both proficiency and engagement are co-constructed. These tools often personalize learning, provide real-time feedback, and foster autonomy—all of which contribute to improved language performance and deeper involvement in the learning process. For example, students who frequently use AI-driven platforms receive tailored linguistic input, which enhances both

accuracy and motivation (Rahimi Zhang, 2023). Similarly, interactive e-books and games not only reinforce language skills but also increase time-on-task and learner satisfaction (Arévalo-Guerrero Rosales-Pérez, 2023). Research has shown that a positive correlation exists between student engagement and proficiency outcomes. In a study by Guerra Ayala et al. (2024), students who reported high enjoyment and consistent engagement with English learning apps also demonstrated significant gains in oral proficiency. These findings underscore the importance of integrating instructional strategies and digital interventions that simultaneously promote skill development and foster learner involvement. Table 2 presents a consolidated overview of the extent of student proficiency and engagement in English language acquisition based on four key dimensions: English language proficiency, engagement, intent and motivation, and perception on digital tools. The computed mean average of 3.88, interpreted as ‘Extensive,’ affirms that secondary students demonstrate a high level of competence, interest, and motivation in learning English, particularly when supported by digitally enhanced learning environments. The highest mean was recorded for English language proficiency (M = 4.08), indicating that students perceive themselves as effectively developing their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. This is followed by engagement (M = 3.96), reflect-

ing active participation in classroom activities, sustained attention, and collaborative interactions. Intent and motivation (M = 3.86) also scored highly, indicating that students exhibit a goal-oriented approach, persistence, and eagerness to improve their English performance.

Lastly, perception on digital tools (M = 3.60), while still categorized as “Extensive,” received the lowest rating, which may point to varying degrees of enthusiasm or differing experiences with specific technologies.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Student Proficiency and Engagement

No	Extent of Student Proficiency and Engagement	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	English language proficiency	134	4.08	Extensive
2	Engagement	134	3.96	Extensive
3	Intent and Motivation	134	3.86	Extensive
4	Perception on digital tools	134	3.60	Extensive
Mean Average		134	3.88	Extensive

These findings are consistent with international and local studies that have underscored the interplay of cognitive, behavioral, and affective factors in successful language acquisition. Guerra Ayala et al. (2024) linked positive student enjoyment and motivation to greater proficiency in oral English among pre-service teachers. Similarly, Rahimi and Zhang (2023) found that when digital tools are personalized and feedback-rich, they significantly enhance both engagement and perceived language competence. In the Philippine context, De Vera and Del Rosario (2022) noted that students with strong motivation and supportive perceptions of educational technology showed improved linguistic performance and task completion rates. Overall, the data presented in Table 11 validate that the integration of digital tools, combined

with strong pedagogical design, promotes not only language proficiency but also a sustained culture of engagement and self-directed learning among secondary students.

3.3. *Significant Relationship between Utilizing Digital Tools and Student Proficiency and Engagement*—Table 3 displays the result of the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between the utilization of digital tools and student proficiency and engagement in English language acquisition. The study yielded an r-value of 0.046 with a p-value of 0.596, indicating a very weak positive correlation that is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level. Based on this outcome, the null hypothesis (H)—which posits that there is no significant relationship between the two variables—is accepted.

The results suggest that although digital tools are extensively used in the classroom (as reflected in earlier tables), their utilization alone does not significantly predict or influence student proficiency and engagement. This may

imply that the mere presence or availability of digital tools does not automatically translate to improved learning outcomes. Rather, the quality of implementation, teacher facilitation, student digital literacy, and pedagogical alignment may

Table 3. Relationship between Utilizing Digital Tools and Student Proficiency and Engagement

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Utilizing Digital Tools	0.046	0.596	Not Significant	Accept H ₀

**Significant at p < 0.05*

be more critical in leveraging technology for meaningful language learning experiences. This finding is echoed in the literature. For instance, Wang and Vásquez (2021) argued that while digital tools enhance accessibility, they may fall short in driving engagement or proficiency without guided instruction and contextualized usage. Similarly, Sung, Yang, and Lee (2022) concluded that the educational impact of technology depends heavily on the integration strategy and how well it supports student-centered pedagogies. In a Philippine context, De Vera and Del Rosario (2022) emphasized that effective learning outcomes with digital tools arise only

when students are scaffolded and actively supported by teachers in navigating and applying such tools. These studies affirm that digital tools are enablers, not determinants, and their impact is mediated by instructional design, teacher expertise, and student motivation. In summary, while digital tools are widely perceived as beneficial and are extensively used, their utilization in isolation does not statistically influence students' English language proficiency and engagement. This calls for a more deliberate and pedagogically informed approach to technology integration in language instruction

3.4. Utilization of Digital Tools Influences Student Proficiency and Engagement —The Model Summary table presents the predictive capacity of the regression model analyzing how various forms of digital tool utilization influence student proficiency and engagement. The baseline model (M), which includes no predictors, shows an R² = 0.000, indicating no explanatory power. In contrast, the full model (M), which includes five predictor variables—DTLLA (Language Learning Apps), DT-IEB (Interactive E-Books), DT-VC (Virtual Classrooms), DG-LBG (Language-Based Games), and DT-AIDT (AI-Driven Tools)—produces an R = 0.330, R² = 0.109, and an Adjusted R² = 0.074. This suggests that approximately 11% of the variance in student proficiency and engagement can be explained by the collective influence of these digital tools. Although the model shows a modest predictive power, the reduction in RMSE (from

0.216 to 0.208) indicates an improvement in model fit with the addition of the predictors. Table 4 shows the individual contributions of each type of digital tool to student proficiency and engagement: Language-Based Games showed a significant negative effect (= -0.266, t = -2.983, p = .003). This finding, while unexpected, suggests that over reliance on gamification without structured learning outcomes may reduce effectiveness. This aligns with Wang and Vásquez (2021), who cautioned that digital games may entertain but not always translate into language mastery if not pedagogically aligned. AI-Driven Tools had a significant positive effect (= 0.284, t = 2.605, p = .010), indicating their utility in enhancing personalized learning and feedback. This supports the findings of Rahimi and Zhang (2023), who observed that adaptive AI technologies improve learner engagement and academic performance in ESL settings.

Table 4. Utilization of Digital Tools Influences Student Proficiency and Engagement

Model	B	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
M ₀ (Intercept)	3.879	0.019	—	208.203	< .001	—
M ₁ (Intercept)	3.909	0.211	—	18.566	< .001	—
DTLLA_AVE	0.004	0.023	0.014	0.165	0.869	Accept Null
DT_IEB_AVE	0.031	0.020	0.133	1.594	0.113	Accept Null
DT_VC_AVE	-0.061	0.044	-0.147	-1.383	0.169	Accept Null
DG_LBG_AVE	-0.107	0.036	-0.266	-2.983	0.003	Reject Null
DT_AIDT_AVE	0.124	0.047	0.284	2.605	0.010	Reject Null

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations of the study based on the findings derived from both quantitative and qualitative phases. Anchored in the explanatory sequential mixed-method design, this chapter synthesizes the statistical results and participants' standpoints to address the research problems. The conclusions reflect the essential insights drawn from the extent of digital tool utilization and its influence on student proficiency and engagement in English language acquisition. Furthermore, grounded recommendations are offered to inform pedagogical practices, policy directions, and future research initiatives.

4.1. Findings—The study found that the extent of utilization of digital tools in English language acquisition was extensive across all five categories. Among them, language learning apps (M = 3.96) and AI-driven tools (M = 3.92) were notably emphasized for their personalized and skill-targeted features. Language-based games (M = 3.91) were also extensively used, offering engaging ways to reinforce learning. Interactive e-books (M = 3.75) and virtual classrooms (M = 3.73) were regularly integrated, supporting diverse learner needs and promoting reading and collaboration. The overall mean average of 3.85 indicates a strong adoption of these tools within the secondary English curriculum. The results revealed that students demonstrated extensive levels of proficiency and engagement. English language proficiency was highest among the indicators (M = 4.08), signifying improved reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills. Engagement (M = 3.96) and intent and motivation (M = 3.86) also reflected positively, as students actively participated in class and pursued language development independently. Their perception of digital tools (M = 3.60) was likewise extensive, though slightly lower, suggesting overall satisfaction but with room for improving ease of use and alignment with learner preferences. Based on the correlation analysis, there was no significant overall relationship between the general utilization of digital tools and student proficiency and engagement ($r = 0.046$, $p = 0.596$). This indicates that while digital tools are widely used, their impact on proficiency and engagement may not be uniformly felt across all tools or learning contexts. The regression analysis showed that AI-driven tools had a significant positive influence on student proficiency and engagement ($\beta = 0.284$, $p = .010$), affirming their role in providing adap-

tive feedback and personalized learning experiences. Conversely, language-based games had a significant negative influence ($\beta = -0.266$, $p = .003$), suggesting that while engaging, they may require improved instructional alignment to be effective. Other tools—language learning apps, interactive e-books, and virtual classrooms—did not register significant predictive effects. The qualitative analysis revealed five major themes: (1) Selective Impact of Tools, where teachers acknowledged that only certain tools like AI-based platforms had substantial effects; (2) Contextual Effectiveness, indicating that the utility of tools depends on instructional context; (3) Pedagogical Mediation, underscoring the critical role of teacher guidance; (4) Motivation and Language Growth, highlighting the affective benefits of digital tools; and (5) Balanced Integration, calling for a blended approach. These standpoints clarified why a general statistical relationship may not be evident and emphasized the conditional effectiveness of digital tools. Participants expressed nuanced views, explaining that not all digital tools yield equal outcomes. They emphasized that tools like AI-driven platforms promote significant gains, while others, such as games, may distract unless carefully implemented. Their insights support the regression findings and reinforce the importance of teacher-led integration and instructional fit. The standpoints provide context to the statistical outcome, affirming that the relationship is not uniformly significant but is dependent on the quality, appropriateness, and pedagogical use of the tools.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: Extensive Utilization of Digital Tools The integration of digital tools in English language instruction—particularly language learning apps, AI-driven tools, and language-based games—was found to be extensive. This suggests that schools and teachers are actively adopting technology to support language ac-

quisition, with various tools serving different instructional functions. High Levels of Student Proficiency and Engagement Students demonstrated extensive English language proficiency, strong engagement, and high intent and motivation, suggesting that the digital learning environment is conducive to language development. However, perceptions of digital tools were slightly lower, indicating a need to evaluate tool accessibility and user experience. Non-Significant Overall Relationship Between Digital Tool Use and Outcomes

The study found no statistically significant overall relationship between digital tool utilization and student proficiency and engagement. This implies that usage alone does not guarantee effectiveness and underscores the need for contextually appropriate and pedagogically guided implementation. Specific Digital Tools Influence Learning Outcomes Among the digital tools, AI-driven tools significantly and positively influenced student proficiency and engagement, highlighting their potential for adaptive and personalized instruction. In contrast, language-based games showed a negative impact, possibly due to insufficient alignment with learning objectives or excessive reliance on gamification. Conditional Effectiveness Based on Pedagogical Factors Qualitative findings affirmed that the effectiveness of digital tools is mediated by how they are integrated into instruction. Participants emphasized that teacher facilitation, alignment with curriculum goals, and student digital competence determine the success of digital tool utilization.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the above conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: Prioritize Pedagogically-Aligned Integration of Digital Tools Teachers and curriculum developers should not only adopt digital tools but ensure that their use is directly aligned with instructional goals and responsive to students' language proficiency levels. Promote the Use of AI-Driven Tools for Tar-

geted Language Instruction Given their positive impact, AI-driven tools should be prioritized in instructional planning. Training teachers on how to effectively utilize such tools can enhance personalized learning and improve student outcomes.

Re-evaluate the Role of Language-Based Games Although engaging, language-based games must be redesigned or selected carefully to ensure they reinforce rather than distract from core language skills. Developers and teachers should collaborate to evaluate the pedagogical value of these tools. Provide Continuous Professional Development Educators should receive sustained professional development on digital pedagogy, tool selection, and technology-mediated instruction to maximize the educational benefits of digital tools. Conduct Learner-

Centered Evaluation of Digital Tools Schools should involve students in evaluating the effectiveness and usability of digital tools. Their feedback can guide improvements in tool selection, user interface design, and implementation strategies. Strengthen Blended Learning Approaches A balanced integration of traditional and digital methods should be promoted to ensure holistic and inclusive learning experiences that cater to diverse learners and mitigate digital fatigue or dependency.

Further Research on Long-Term Impacts Future studies may examine the long-term effects of digital tool usage on language acquisition, focusing on student retention, critical thinking, and communicative competence in authentic settings.

5. References

- Afify, M. K., Alqoot, A. M., & Zedan, S. A. K. (2023). Criteria for designing and evaluating the quality of virtual classrooms during emergency learning. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 24(4), 160–174. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.1305532>
- Aizawa, I., Rose, H., Thompson, G., & Curle, S. (2023). Beyond the threshold: Exploring english language proficiency, linguistic challenges, and academic language skills of japanese students in an english medium instruction programme. *Language Teaching Research*, 27(4), 837–861. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168820965510>
- Alnajashi, A. (2024). Exploring the interplay of motivation, international posture, and online informal english learning: A mixed-methods study. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 13(2), 106–118. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v13n2p106>
- Al-Qahtani, M. F. (2021). Task-based language teaching and its impact on learners' proficiency in english as a second language. *Asian EFL Journal*, 28(3), 205–225.
- Al-Shara, I. A., & Al-Khalidi, M. F. (2023). Digital language games and grammar acquisition in secondary esl contexts. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 7(2), 113–126. <https://doi.org/10.31681/jetol.1278540>
- Archibald, A., Hudson, C., Heap, T., Thompson, R. R., Lin, L., DeMeritt, J., & Lucke, H. (2023). A validation of ai-enabled discussion platform metrics and relationships to student efforts. *TechTrends*, 67(2), 285–293.
- Arévalo-Guerrero, E., & Rosales-Pérez, M. (2023). Interactive e-books and reading comprehension in esl learners: A multimedia-based study. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 14(2), 317–326. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1402.06>

- Arndt, S. (2022). Construction and validation of a questionnaire to study engagement in informal second language learning. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 44(3), 649–673. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263122000194>
- Balić, N., Grubišić, A., & Granić, A. (2023). Perceptions of digital learning and teaching: The case of a croatian university transition to an emergency digital environment. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning*, 28(1), 453–481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10758-023-09692-4>
- Bautista, A., Garcia, M., & Delgado, C. (2023). The role of ai-driven tools in promoting student engagement and language acquisition. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 58(4), 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0034034X.2023.2012143>
- Brandmiller, C., Schnitzler, K., & Dumont, H. (2024). Teacher perceptions of student motivation and engagement: Longitudinal associations with student outcomes. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 39(2), 1397–1420. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-023-00665-7>
- Burila, J. M. P. (2021). Musichemistry on grade eight learners' motivation, engagement and proficiency in chemistry. *Journal of Science and Mathematics Education in Southeast Asia*, 44, Article 7.
- BusinessWorld. (2023). The ethical implications of ai in philippine education: Privacy concerns and future challenges.
- Capulong, H. S., & de Guzman, F. A. (2021). Exploring the effectiveness of virtual classrooms in english instruction during the pandemic: A philippine experience. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(2), 25–34.
- Cilligöl Karabey, S., & Karaman, S. (2024). Identifying pedagogical design and implementation of synchronous virtual classrooms. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 25(2), 132–153. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v25i2.7220>
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2019). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd). SAGE Publications.
- De Mesa, R. J., & Padrinao, M. E. (2022). Enhancing vocabulary and engagement through interactive e-books among junior high school students. *Philippine Journal of Educational Studies*, 5(1), 55–67.
- De Vera, R. A., & Del Rosario, J. C. (2022). Enhancing learner engagement in english language classes through digital enrichment activities. *Philippine Journal of Educational Measurement and Evaluation*, 12(1), 55–68.
- Educause. (2023). Challenges and concerns about technology's role in education. *EDUCAUSE Review*. <https://www.educause.edu>
- García, R., & Alvarez, L. (2021). The effectiveness of language learning apps in secondary education: Improving vocabulary and pronunciation. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(3), 121–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jedutech.2021.03.004>
- Lee, Y., & Chen, W. (2021). Teacher-student interaction and language development: Exploring the role of social scaffolding in learning environments. *Language Learning*, 71(1), 125–142. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12419>
- Li, L., & Wang, X. (2024). Investigating english vocabulary acquisition efficiency using digital tools: A return-on-investment perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(1), 123–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12078-9>

- Li, Y. (2024). Usability of chatgpt in second language acquisition: Capabilities, effectiveness, applications, challenges, and solutions. *Studies in Applied Linguistics & TESOL*, 24(1), 24–37. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1435560.pdf>
- Lim, B. C.-Y., Liu, L. W.-L., & Choo, C.-H. (2020). Investigating the effects of interactive e-book towards academic achievement. *Asian Journal of University Education*, 16(3), 78–88. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v16i3.10272>
- Lopez, M. K. R. R., & Ortega-Dela Cruz, R. A. (2022). Gallery walk technique in enhancing reading comprehension and oral english language proficiency of junior high school students. *Waikato Journal of Education*, 27(3), 57–71. <https://doi.org/10.15663/wje.v27i3.813>
- Lumbantoruan, J. H. (2024). The impact of student engagement and motivation in the statistics learning process. *REDIMAT - Journal of Research in Mathematics Education*, 13(1), 1–22.
- Mahmoodi, M. H., & Ifinedo, P. (2022). Investigating the effects of ai-based adaptive learning on motivation and engagement in esl classrooms. *Computers & Education*, 184, 104517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104517>
- Martin, D., & Nair, S. (2022). Virtual classrooms in secondary education: Enhancing student engagement and language proficiency. *Journal of Language Teaching and Learning*, 34(2), 89–102. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02108954.2022.2014390>
- McLeod, M., & Cheng, L. (2023). The canadian english language proficiency index program (celPIP) test. *Language Assessment Quarterly*, 20(3), 339–352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15434303.2023.2237487>
- Musliadi, M., Triyono, S., & Jamilah, J. (2024). Enhancing speaking agility: Unveiling indonesian lecturers' hybrid teaching experiences in oral communication skills. *Language Learning in Higher Education*, 14(1), 123–145. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cercles-2024-0018>
- of Education (DepEd), D. (2023). Annual report on the integration of technology in philippine education. *Department of Education*. <https://www.deped.gov.ph>
- Siregar, G., Bismala, L., Hafisah, H., Handayani, S., Manurung, Y. H., Andriany, D., & Hasibuan, L. S. (2023). Unveiling determinant of student engagement. *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, 17(2), 174–182. <https://doi.org/10.11591/edulearn.v17i2.20747>
- Smith, D. L. (2023). *Integrating artificial intelligence tools in secondary education: Effects on student engagement and learning outcomes* [Doctoral dissertation]. ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global [UMI No. 29064289].
- Smith, J., & Jones, T. (2022). Revisiting nativism in the context of neurocognitive language research. *Journal of Linguistic Theory*, 38(2), 234–247. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jlt.206>
- Söderlund, M., & Lundeberg, M. (2021). Behavioral learning through digital tools: Reinforcement principles in language learning apps. *Computers & Education*, 162, 104108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.104108>
- Soriano, J. C., & Ramirez, L. J. (2021). Effectiveness of ai-powered english learning tools among filipino high school learners. *Asian Journal of Language Studies*, 9(2), 45–59.
- Su, F., Zou, D., Xie, H., & Wang, F. L. (2021). A comparative review of mobile and non-mobile games for language learning. *SAGE Open*, 11(4), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211067247>

- Sung, Y. T., Yang, J. M., & Lee, H. Y. (2022). Educational affordances of mobile and digital tools in language learning: A meta-analysis. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 70(1), 107–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-021-10041-9>
- Teng, Y., & Wang, X. (2024). Full caption, english proficiency and their relationships with behavioral, cognitive and emotional student engagement in chinese efl college content-based instruction video learning. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(1), 861–880. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12342-y>
- Times), F. ((2023). Youth talks: Students reveal their hopes and fears for ai. *Financial Times*. <https://www.ft.com>
- UNESCO. (2023). The digital divide in education: Issues and solutions [Accessed 2025-06-21].
- Uygun, M., & Çayirli, E. (2024). Virtual classroom management competency of classroom teachers. *International Technology and Education Journal*, 8(1), 36–46. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1445448.pdf>
- Villanueva, M. A., & Dimapilis, D. T. (2021). Enhancing english language teaching through localized language games: A philippine classroom experience. *Asian Journal of Educational Research*, 9(4), 34–42.
- Vo, H., & Ho, H. (2024). Online learning environment and student engagement: The mediating role of expectancy and task value beliefs. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 51(2), 2183–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-024-00689-1>
- Wang, S., & Vásquez, C. (2021). Exploring student engagement with mobile-assisted language learning: A qualitative study. *ReCALL*, 33(3), 261–278. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S095834402000037X>
- Wang, X., & Xu, J. (2023). Digital platforms and collaborative language learning: Enhancing language acquisition in virtual social spaces. *Language and Technology*, 12(1), 75–89. <https://doi.org/10.1007/lt.2023.0044>
- Webber, E. (2024). Mixed methods research explained: Combine data like a pro. from heatmaps to interviews, here’s how to blend qualitative and quantitative data for holistic user insights [Accessed 2025-06-21].
- York, J., Poole, F. J., & deHaan, J. W. (2021). Playing a new game: An argument for a teacher-focused field around games and play in language education. *Foreign Language Annals*, 54(1), 219–231. <https://doi.org/10.1111/flan.12585>
- Yuen, L. P., & Schlote, B. (2024). Exploring the use of mobile applications for l2 learning in higher education. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 53(1), 45–68. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00472395241238693>
- Zhang, M., Jiang, Q., Xiong, W., Li, Q., & Zhao, W. (2024). Self-efficacy predicting k–12 students’ self-directed learning with mobile technology: Analyzing the mediating role of student engagement. *Educational Technology & Society*, 27(3), 236–252. [https://doi.org/10.30191/ETS.202407_27\(3\).SP03](https://doi.org/10.30191/ETS.202407_27(3).SP03)